

ACCOUNTING FOR RESIDENCE IN RESIDENCES ANALYSIS OF LANDSCAPE PROBLEMS.

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Annotation: *Cases of step-by-step application of the main tasks in solving landscape problems, taking into account the relief of settlements. It is said that the correct calculation and evaluation of the relief will show the effect on the existing landscape of the existing structure.*

Keywords: *landscape, relief, macrorelief, microrelief, mesorelief, hemorrhage, geological, hydrological.*

The word "landscape" comes from the German "Land" - "earth", "schaft" - "landscape" means Generalizer of typological natural complexes concepts. These include geological soil, topography, climate, soils, flora, fauna and hydrological regime and natural boundaries. The term "landscape" geography was first introduced almost simultaneously by A. A. Borzov. L.S. Berg. Thanks to the scientific work of D. F. Morozov, the word natural-geographical sculpture introduced as a synonym. Further deepening the landscape concept and a group of natural scientists in the process of refining its definition split. Particular attention is paid to landscape research we must recognize the unity and contradiction of the community. Separately. It is impossible to generalize without information about a particular landscape. Hence the objective existence of a landscape on the surface of the earth with certain features generalization, i.e., it is possible to combine different classes, etc. This, the landscape is genetically unified this is total geotism. It has the same geological structure, the same type of relief, the same climate and a dynamic connection that only had to do with the landscape consists of a mathematical sum. Horizontal zone, province the simplest geosystem that forms regional geotimes such as a county or district. She is the second is the simplest and smallest unit of the geographic crust. It is smaller than itself, as numerous as the facies, and dynamic. The landscape is constantly in the process of exchanging matter

and energy with neighboring landscapes. Interactive geotism. In short, all views of the earth are the same. The landscape is called. There are also accommodations. Landscapes are studied by their origin. Planned to build work carried out in the creation of the landscape of the settlement the first is that we need to choose a terrain that suits it. Also about relief information. What is the word for relief? What is the role of terrain in the construction industry? Let's talk about questions. Relief (French, relief, lat. Relevo - I raise) (in geography) - the appearance of the earth's surface, ocean and seabed, districts differ in size, origin, age and history of development. Unevenness: mountain, plain, plateau, hill, plateau, hill, ridge, valley, depression, ravines, rocks and other lowlands. Reliefs are excellent. Divided into **3 types** depending on the size.

1. **MACRORELIEFS.**
2. **MESORELIEFS.**
3. **MICRORELIEFS.**

MACRORELIEFS in large area and **200-1500 m** in height. These include the continental shelf, the ocean floor, as well as. Lesser forms are mountain systems, plains, ranges and mountains. Basins, ridges and lowlands.

MESORELIEFS Average city altitudes (difference **10-200 m**) is a suitable indicator for which hills or citywide depressions heights are determined. These include rocks, underwater channels, hills and more low heights.

MICRORELIEFS is small (**0-10 m**) in height. This is a territory of engineering improvement of streets, sidewalks, residential buildings indicates the height of the entry threshold. The relief is one of the most important and important factors in urban planning with status for a number of activities such as urban planning, irrigation closely connected. Surface relief forms, its development and. The science that studies the distribution of matter is called **geomorphology**.

So, taking into account the above points, the placement made in mesorelief. Housing for people service objects. There is a family life of people style, life experience pass. Permanent residents in residential areas this place is called home. Designs from creating living spaces future home, taking into account the needs of the customer, supply and demand create a model. Features of their landscape when creating structures attention should be paid. First of all, what is the purpose of construction? is being built. Then build on the composition of the relief materials are selected. At high humidity of the relief from the point of view of safety, the foundations are poured deeper, and the fixing piles stumbles. Apply this practice to a

building or structure erected on top of a terrain prevents collapse and sinking of the earth due to pressure. Alternatively outside the building the consequences should also be examined. The climate is rainy cold weather, hot weather and other external influences landscape is created.

When creating a landscape for residential areas, it is important to pay attention to the relief the reason is that its service life is based on the set time. Many in some cases, buildings are filled due to incomplete calculation of the relief cannot serve. Even with increased restoration work won't happen. The settlements are mostly inhabited by individuals and extended families. Considering their safety in the first place, the relief structure is understandable. Landscape issues must be taken into account in the calculation.

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